

36M Progress Report

Project title: “Environmental effects on physical properties of smart composites and FRP modified by carbonaceous nanofillers for structural applications”.

Project No. 1.1.1.2/VIAA/1/16/066.

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**Activity 1.1.1.2 “Post-doctoral Research Aid” of the Specific Aid
Objective 1.1.1 “To increase the research and innovative capacity of
scientific institutions of Latvia and the ability to attract external
financing, investing in human resources and infrastructure” of the
Operational Programme “Growth and Employment”.**

Summary

During the third year of the project the main purpose was to perform seasonal full-year environmental ageing and characterize some mechanical, electrical and thermophysical properties of the epoxy, nanocomposite (NC), unidirectional and symmetrical laminates of basalt fibre-reinforced plastics (neat and modified by 0.03 wt. % of hybrid carbon nanofiller (carbon nanotubes and nanofibers in the ratio 1:1 by mass) after each season. Moreover, water absorption at 20, 50 and 70 °C until equilibrium has been performed for all materials to evaluate the effect of moisture and temperature on all material characteristics studied. As a result, the effect of full-year environmental ageing on the flexural and thermophysical properties of the epoxy, NC and BFRPs was not found to be significant. The relative change of flexural and thermophysical characteristics for all tested materials was within 10-15%. For nano-modified epoxy and FRPs slightly higher effect of absorbed moisture on these characteristics was found which can be attributed to higher defectiveness (e.g. porosity, the formation of agglomerates etc.). Significantly increased electrical conductivity of UD BFRP along fibres due to moisture absorption could be related to the increased electrical conductivity of NC and possible orientation of carbon nanofillers' particles during the manufacturing of the samples. The most environmentally stable and potentially applicable for damage indication is UD BFRP along fibres.

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1. Objectives for the 3rd year of the project

- 1) Characterization of some mechanical, electrical and thermal properties of the epoxy, NC and BFRP after each season of full-year hydrothermal ageing by standard tests and analytical modelling;
- 2) Preparation of conference reports, popular scientific publications, and scientific papers.

2. Explanation of the work carried per WP

WP1. Coordination and management

T1.1. Operational issues

During the third year of the project, several laboratory seminars were carried out in the Institute for Mechanics of Materials, University of Latvia (LU) to evaluate progress and decide on next steps. Four quarter reports were prepared in Latvian for the University of Latvia (LU). 36M public progress report was prepared in English for publishing in *Zenodo* repository (current document). Different communication activities such as e-mails, discussions by *Skype*, sharing of documents and files were performed with the scientific consultant from LU Dr. Sc. Ing. Andrey Aniskevich and the representative person from IPCB Dr. Sc. Ing. Mauro Zarrelli.

T1.2. Scientific management

Post-doctorate monitored the project's progress to the scientific consultant from LU and the representative person from IPCB and followed up the implementation, completing all deliverables assigned in the project proposal. Continuous analysis of risks was carried out by post-doctorate to avoid delays, complete material resource preparation before the given tasks.

T1.3. IPR management

The IPR management was performed according to IPR strategy (D1.3, M4) developed for identifying publishable subject matter, by registering and continuous updating of expected outcomes and foreground generated.

WP2. Design and development of the NC and FRP plate

T2.1. Selection of the most optimal material solution

Completed during the 1st year of the project.

T2.2. Optimization of the NC processing conditions

Completed during the 1st year of the project.

T2.3. Development of NC specimens with single and hybrid fillers

Completed during the 1st year of the project.

T2.4. Design and development of the NC specimens at electrical percolation

Completed during the 2nd year of the project.

T2.5. Design and development of smart FRP plate

Completed during the 2nd year of the project. Additionally, BFRP plates were produced to perform the water absorption tests at 70 °C until equilibrium and verify the effect of moisture and temperature on the flexural, electrical and thermophysical properties.

WP3. Characterization of the NC and FRP

T3.1. Micro- and nanostructural characterization of the NCs

Completed during the 1st year of the project.

T3.2. Standard mechanical, electrical, and thermal characterization

Characterization of the NC and BFRP specimens before and after each season of full-year hydrothermal ageing was carried out. The mechanical properties for epoxy and NC samples were tested under three-point bending mode according to ASTM D790. The flexural modulus, strength and maximal deformation were evaluated from the stress-strain curves. The effect of full-year environmental ageing on the flexural properties of the epoxy, NC and BFRPs was not significant. The relative change of flexural and thermophysical characteristics for all tested materials was within 10-15%. For nano-modified epoxy and FRPs slightly higher effect of absorbed moisture on these characteristics was found which can be attributed to higher defectiveness (e.g. porosity, the formation of agglomerates etc.).

The electrical resistance of the NC samples was measured by using a multimeter DMM 4020 (*Tektronix*) following a two-point methodology. Opposite facets of the samples were covered with conductive silver paint to reduce contact resistance effect. Significantly increased electrical conductivity of UD BFRP along fibres due to moisture absorption could be related to the increased electrical conductivity of NC and possible orientation of carbon nanofillers' particles during the manufacturing of the samples.

The thermal conductivity was measured by using thermal constants analyzer TPS 500 (*Hot Disc*) at a heating power 50 mW and heating time 40 s by using Kapton sensor with radius 3.2 mm. The effect of full-year environmental ageing on the thermal conductivity of the epoxy and NC was not significant. The relative change of thermophysical characteristics for all tested materials was within 10%.

The dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA) was carried out by using a Mettler Toledo DMA/SDTA861 in tensile mode and $T = 30-280$ °C at 3 K/min heating rate to evaluate hygrothermal ageing effects in both initial and environmentally aged NC and BFRP samples. Glass transition temperature for all tested materials obtained from DMTA was almost the same in the initial state and after full-year environmental ageing: 235 ± 2 °C proving that the crosslinking degree was similar in all materials and no significant plasticization occurred in the materials due to moisture absorption.

T3.3. Nonstandard environmental ageing

For the final year the seasonal environmental ageing consisted of 3 months of water absorption for summer ($T = +20$ °C), autumn ($T = +10$ °C), winter ($T = -10$ °C), and spring ($T = +10$ °C) seasons. The peculiarities of moisture absorption in epoxy resin and NC samples were studied. The overall behaviour was similar for all materials following classical Fick's law for 3D moisture diffusion. The diffusivity and equilibrium moisture content of neat and nano-modified epoxy and BFRP were almost the same. For nano-modified epoxy and FRPs slightly higher values of

sorption characteristics were found which can be attributed to higher defectiveness (e.g. porosity, the formation of agglomerates etc.).

WP4. Dissemination, communication and data management

T4.1. Dissemination of results

During the third year of project implementation, 4 quarter press releases (#9-12) were prepared and published on the website of LU (<https://www.lu.lv/zinatne/programmas-un-projekti/es-strukturfondi/1112pasakums-pecdoktoranturas-petniecibas-atbalsts-1karta/vides-ietekme-uz-viedo-ar-oglekla-nanopildvielam-modificetu-kompozitu-un-skiedru-plastikatu-fizikalajam-ipasibam-strukturaliem-pielietojumiem/>).

Based on the project results one scientific paper on hydrothermal ageing of an epoxy resin filled with carbon nanofillers was published in Q1 scientific journal having open access (*Polymers*). One scientific paper on seasonal hydrothermal environmental effects on some physical properties of the epoxy and epoxy-based nanocomposites and basalt fibre-reinforced plastics (BFRP) was submitted to *Polymer Degradation and Stability* (Q1 journal, IF 4.03) by the end of 2020.

For the dissemination of project results among general public one popular scientific publication “Smart materials in external environmental conditions” (in Latvian) was published in news portal of the University of Latvia, <https://www.lu.lv/par-mums/lu-mediji/zinas/zina/t/59232>.

For the same purpose, a professional FACEBOOK profile was updated with 5 press releases (<https://www.facebook.com/tatjana.glaskovakuzmina>) on the project activities during the third year of project implementation.

Four project proposals were prepared and submitted for different scientific calls to assure sustainability and continuity of the project results (2 M-era.Net, 1 Baltic research programme, and 1 Nordic Energy Research).

T4.2. Communication

According to dissemination/communication plan (D4.1, M12) developed during the first year of project implementation certain dissemination/communication activities were carried out.

Several presentations about the project and its current results were made for the progress seminars organized in the Institute for Mechanics of Materials of LU (Riga, Latvia).

A presentation about project results was prepared and reported for the invited lecture at Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Gjøvik, Norway) for PhD course “Advanced materials” on 10.12.2020.

T4.3. Knowledge and data management and protection

All data generated (raw and ready data files, reports, presentations) were transferred to the folder of POSTDOC project in the central database *Dropbox* providing access to scientific supervisor from LU Dr. Sc. Ing. Andrey Aniskevich and representative person of IPCB Dr. Sc. Ing. Mauro Zarrelli. All data files will be preserved in *Dropbox* during the project implementation and at least five years after completion of the project.

3. Main conclusions

The effect of full-year environmental ageing on the flexural and thermophysical properties of the epoxy, NC and BFRPs was not significant. The relative change of flexural and thermophysical characteristics for all tested materials was within 10-15%.

For nano-modified epoxy and FRPs slightly higher effect of absorbed moisture on these characteristics was found which can be attributed to higher defectiveness (e.g. porosity, the formation of agglomerates etc.).

Significantly increased electrical conductivity of UD BFRP along fibres due to moisture absorption could be related to the increased electrical conductivity of NC and possible orientation of carbon nanofillers' particles during the manufacturing of the samples.

Satisfactory correlation between the change of electrical conductivity and strain was obtained for all conductive materials.

The most environmentally stable and potentially applicable for damage indication is UD BFRP along fibres.

4. Main results

Scientific publications

1. Glaskova-Kuzmina T., Aniskevich A., Zotti A., Borriello A. and Zarrelli M. "Flexural properties of the epoxy resin filled with single and hybrid carbon nanofillers". Journal of Physics: Conference Series, 2020, 1431, 012001. DOI: 10.1088/1742-6596/1431/1/012001.
2. Glaskova-Kuzmina T., Aniskevich A., Sevchenko J., Borriello A., and Zarrelli M. Moisture sorption by epoxy resin filled with MWCNT of different thickness. Proceedings of European Conference on Composite Materials 2018, 2020, Athens, Greece, code 155810.
3. Glaskova-Kuzmina T., Aniskevich A., Papanicolaou G., Portan D., Zotti A., Borriello A., and Zarrelli M. Hydrothermal aging of an epoxy resin filled with carbon nanofillers. Polymers, 2020, Vol. 12, 1153; DOI:10.3390/polym12051153.

Popular scientific publications

1. Tatjana Glaskova-Kuzmina. Smart materials in external environmental conditions (in Latvian). News portal of the University of Latvia, 2020, <https://www.lu.lv/par-mums/lu-mediji/zinas/zina/t/59232>.

Submitted project proposals

1. "Sustainable and durable basalt fibre reinforced plastics for efficient urban transport", Baltic Research Programme 2020, Project coordinator Tatjana Glaskova-Kuzmina (the proposal was submitted in October 2020 and is under consideration).
2. "Polymer composite construction reinforced with a customized 3D fabric", M-Era.Net 2020, Project leader from LU Tatjana Glaskova-Kuzmina (full proposal has been submitted in November 2020 and is under consideration).

3. “Predictive Multiparametric Modelling for Optimal Repair of Composite Wind Turbine Blades”, Baltic-Nordic Energy Research Programme 2020. Project coordinator Tatjana Glaskova-Kuzmina (the proposal didn’t meet the criteria and was rejected).

4. “Smart High-Performance Composites for Energy & Transport”, M-Era.Net 2020, Project leader from LU Tatjana Glaskova-Kuzmina (the pre-proposal didn’t meet the criteria and was rejected).

Presentations at international conferences

No presentations were made in 2020 because of the cancellation of the planned conference (ICSAAM 2020, Patras, Greece) due to COVID-19. Therefore, the focus was made on the preparation of scientific papers and project proposals instead of presenting the results at international conferences.

5. Deviations from the working plan

Positive deviations from the working plan of dissemination/communication were obtained. The total number of conference presentations and published scientific papers written in the project proposal (2 presentations and 2 scientific papers) is higher (6 presentations and 7 publications indexed in Scopus/WoS) maximizing the impact of the project.

6. Corrective actions

-Participation in online study courses “Theoretical and practical guide to the proposal writing of H2020/Horizon Europe projects” and “Financial management of H2020 projects theoretical and practical approach” organized by EFMC in 2020 to improve professional skills in writing and management of project proposals.

-Preparation and submission of 4 project proposals for different scientific calls to assure sustainability and continuity of the project results (2 M-Era.Net, 1 Baltic research programme, and 1 Nordic Energy Research).

7. Deliverables and Milestones for the reporting period (M25-M36)

Table 1. List of deliverables

No.	Deliverable name	W P	Type	Diss. level	Date
D3.4	Conference report#2 on the environmental effects on the behaviour of the NCs	3	PU	OTHER	M32
D3.5	Scientific paper#2 on environmental effects on the behaviour of the NCs and FRP submitted for publication	3	PU	OTHER	M36
D1.1	Annual LU MMI progress seminars (M12, M24, M36)	1	PU	OTHER	M36
D1.2	Annual public reports published (M12, M24, M36)	1	PU	R	M36
D4.1	Dissemination/communication plan and annual dissemination/communication report (M12, M24, M36)	4	PU	R	M36

Type: R- report, OTHER.

Diss. level: CO -confidential, PU – public.